

The age of storage: Batteries primed for India's power markets

Extreme price swings in wholesale electricity markets and growing concerns around grid instability are opening up new markets for energy storage. Batteries are now a critical solution to drive value for both capital and consumers.

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About

This is the first report in a two-part series exploring the growing role of batteries in India's power sector.

Part 1 – Batteries for power markets examines merchant battery models – where batteries operate without fixed contracts, participating in wholesale day-ahead markets and delivering essential grid services.

Part 2 – Battery through contracts will focus on battery applications enabled by long-term contracts, such as firming up renewables through India's Firm and Dispatchable Renewable Energy (FDRE) framework and peak shaving by distribution utilities.

Together, the series highlights how batteries are unlocking new economic and operational value across India's power sector.

Highlights

1/6

Share of hours in 2024 when prices on power exchanges peaked above INR 9/kWh

2024

Was the first time that potential revenue from battery participation in power exchanges exceeded annualised capital costs

17%

Potential internal rate of return (IRR) on battery storage projects participating in India's Day Ahead Market, starting from 2024

Battery storage set to charge India's wholesale power markets

Battery participation in power markets, without long-term contracts, has often been viewed as a low-return business riddled with uncertain revenue streams. But India's evolving electricity landscape has created an environment where battery energy storage systems (BESS) can earn strong returns from power exchanges, while offering critical system-level support to the grid.

Batteries are increasingly recognised as the multitool of the power sector transition. A flexible solution capable of addressing various challenges emanating from a high-renewables grid, from storing low-cost renewable energy to ensuring real-time grid stability, batteries solve several problems. Yet their large-scale deployment has, until recently, been constrained by high upfront costs and uncertain revenue streams.

As more variable renewable energy enters India's electricity grid, coinciding with sharp declines in battery costs, new business cases are emerging for BESS. One particularly promising opportunity is battery participation in India's wholesale power and ancillary services market.

Price volatility in the day-ahead market segment of the power exchanges is becoming the norm. Electricity prices are now regularly crashing during solar hours and surging during the evenings and nights.

BESS can buy electricity, charge when prices are low and sell when the rates surge. This unique ability allows them to not only generate revenue from the market inefficiency but also reduce the volatility over time. The report finds that this kind of arbitrage alone is enough to recover the full lifecycle costs of BESS.

Add ancillary (grid balancing) services, and the scenario improves further. Batteries' ability to store energy and ramp quickly can fundamentally reshape how grid balancing reserves have worked in India. While serving this crucial role for the grid, BESS can actually get paid for drawing electricity when there is an excess in the system.

Since revenue realisation over the lifetime of a merchant BESS project is closely tied to the market inefficiencies they would address, it is essential to assess these issues with a forward-looking lens, especially in the context of a changing energy mix. Yet, even under conservative assumptions, the report finds that batteries show attractive returns across varying cost and efficiency levels, with shorter duration BESS showing even better revenue prospects.

With the regulatory groundwork in place and the economics making sense, BESS, even without long-term power purchase agreements, appears poised to balance a renewables-heavy grid while delivering strong returns.

01 **Power exchange prices in India's Day Ahead Market hovered near the price cap in one out of every six hours between 2022 and 2024**

Instances of very high prices above INR 9/kilowatt-hour (kWh), with the current price cap at INR 10/kWh, have largely occurred during late evening hours between June and October, driven by costlier coal or gas generators setting the market clearing price.

02 **Average midday power prices fell by nearly 20% from 2022 to 2024 during the summer months, impacting merchant solar revenues**

Midday day-ahead market price declines due to oversupply during solar hours have become increasingly common. This trend has reduced revenue realisation for merchant solar, with capture rates averaging ~65% between 2022 and 2024. This highlights a growing mismatch between when solar generates and when the market pays well.

03 **Batteries can earn enough from pure arbitrage to recover their full lifecycle costs**

After years of falling battery costs and growing revenue from power exchanges, merchant BESS became financially viable from 2024. BESS costs have declined 80% since 2015, with the 2024 levelised storage costs (2-hour) estimated at INR 1.7 million/megawatt-hour (MWh). Over the same period, potential revenues from India's Day Ahead Market have grown fivefold, reaching INR 2.4 million/MWh in 2024. This marks a turning point for merchant BESS investment.

04 **Merchant BESS projects commissioned in 2024 can deliver an IRR of up to 24%**

A system installed in 2025 can earn ~INR 2.7 million/MWh/year from day-ahead market arbitrage, plus INR 0.7 million/MWh/year from ancillary services, averaged over its lifetime. However, the uncertainty in how market prices evolve and the value capture efficiency will determine the actual revenue realisation.

05 **BESS delivers attractive returns even under conditions of cost uncertainty and technical variability**

A system installed in 2024 can achieve a 17% IRR from energy arbitrage alone. Considering an expected 5% variation in depth of discharge, round-trip efficiency and system costs, merchant BESS returns vary between 15.5% and 18%.

06 **Shorter duration (1-2hr) merchant BESS currently offer better returns as compared to a 4hr system**

Merchant BESS with 1-2 hour durations earn higher IRRs (15-22%) than 4-hour systems (13-18%) because of their ability to exploit greater price arbitrage through faster charge-discharge cycles.

07 **Grid balancing services can top up revenues for merchant BESS**

Batteries, due to their fast-acting nature, are well-suited to provide real-time grid balancing reserves. Newly opened market segments like India's Secondary Reserve Ancillary Services (SRAS) offer a revenue stream for this capability.

Energy transition, and the ensuing higher share of variable renewables in the energy mix, is driving extreme intra-day price swings and a shortage of ancillary services at the grid. This is both a risk and an opportunity, and battery storage appears well placed to capitalise on this. There are multiple use cases for batteries: participation in the merchant market is one that's been somewhat under-appreciated till now. This report delves deeper into the expected return profile; developers and investors can use this analysis in order to evaluate this particular market, when they take decisions to allocate capital to different resources/markets.

Satyadeep Jain

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The report has come out at the right time when battery energy storage has become integral from a renewable energy penetration as well as a grid reliability point of view. Thought provoking read for all the stakeholders.

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Wholesale electricity markets will play a crucial role in accelerating renewable energy uptake in India by providing transparent price signals that reflect system needs. Persistent price volatility in the Day Ahead Market and reserve shortages in ancillary service markets are both pointing to a growing demand for flexibility. The emerging arbitrage opportunities and ancillary service incentives are now strong enough to make battery investments bankable.

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Batteries address a range of imminent challenges across the power sector, making them one of the most valuable infrastructure bets of the coming decade.

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Batteries are the ultimate multitool that the Indian power system needs

Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS) can deliver a wide range of services to the power sector. From firming variable renewable power supply to reducing price fluctuations in power markets and stabilising grids, their roles are diverse and expanding.

At the 26th United Nations Conference of the Parties (COP26), India's Prime Minister Narendra Modi [announced](#) a target of 500 gigawatts (GW) of non-fossil fuel capacity by 2030. While not formally part of India's nationally determined contributions (NDCs), this goal remains central to national energy planning, including the 14th National Electricity Plan ([NEP-14](#)).

By June 2025, India had installed a cumulative [168 GW](#) of solar and wind capacity, with [145 GW](#) in the pipeline. NEP-14 projects solar and wind to supply over 50% of total generation by 2032, reaching 365 GW and 122 GW, respectively. To support this, the country needs to integrate storage of 74 GW / 411 gigawatt-hours (GWh) (27 GW / 175 GWh of pumped storage and 47 GW / 236 GWh of BESS) by 2032 as per NEP-14.

As of June 2024, India had [500 MWh](#) of operational BESS and a development pipeline of [121 GWh](#) – 62 GWh under execution and 59 GWh in the tendering stage.

BESS integration can happen at various stages of the electricity system, whether co-located with generators, embedded within transmission and distribution networks or deployed behind the meter for end consumers. The ability to site and size BESS assets based on system needs makes them highly flexible operationally, enabling them to deliver services at multiple points across the grid.

1.1. The many roles of batteries in a renewables-dominated grid

As variable renewable energy penetration grows, the system value of BESS for different applications will continue to increase. Some of the key applications of grid-scale batteries are:

- **Firming up renewable power**

Dispatchability: Coupling renewables with BESS allows the delivery of variable renewable power on demand, making it firm and dispatchable.

Schedule compliance: BESS helps renewable generators adhere to their committed generation schedules by compensating for short-term deviations and avoiding associated penalties.

- **Shifting renewable power across time and space**

Energy arbitrage: BESS enables time-shifting of electricity by storing low-cost renewable energy and discharging it when prices or demand are high. This can also provide congestion relief in grids during oversupply.

Load management: BESS placed on the distribution side can discharge during peak demand hours, helping defer transmission upgrades.

- **Ancillary services:** The fast ramping capability of BESS makes it one of the most effective technologies for delivering critical grid services. They can

support grid stability by helping maintain frequency and voltage within prescribed limits. They can also assist in restoring power after a large-scale outage, commonly referred to as a black start.

1.2. The opportunity for marketcraft

This report explores key merchant BESS applications in India where the asset operates without fixed contracts and earns revenue by participating in various segments of power markets:

- **Energy arbitrage in wholesale electricity markets:** BESS captures value by storing electricity during low price periods, often aligned with solar surplus hours, and discharging during high price periods, typically coinciding with high demand.
- **Provision of frequency regulation in the ancillary services market:** BESS can inject or absorb power to balance supply and demand in the grid. Its fast ramping capability helps maintain frequency within acceptable limits and supports overall grid stability.

A core principle of merchant BESS applications is that revenues are proportional to the challenges they help solve. In this case, the challenge is managing price volatility and frequency fluctuations. This report begins by assessing the outlook on these critical challenges (Chapter 2). It then explores the revenue opportunities they unlock for BESS in India's evolving power markets (Chapter 3).

As price volatility and ancillary reserve gaps grow, so does the need for batteries

Batteries are becoming essential to address the growing challenges of electricity price volatility and ancillary reserve shortfalls. Given current trends in India's short-term power markets, both the need for and the opportunity around batteries are likely to grow in importance.

2.1. The challenge of price volatility

The ability of BESS to charge during low-price surplus periods and discharge during high-price peaks makes it well-suited to manage price volatility. However, the core principle remains: the revenue opportunity of merchant BESS is proportional to the magnitude of the problem it addresses - in this case, the extent of price volatility.

Therefore, before committing to large-scale investments, two questions become critical from an investment perspective: What does price volatility look like today, and how is it likely to evolve? And what specific, persistent market problem is the battery solving? Gaining clarity on these questions is essential for making informed decisions.

2.1.1. Understanding the short-term power market size in India

Short-term power markets give utilities and large consumers the flexibility to meet peak demand and adjust for load variability without overcommitting to long-term power purchase agreements (PPAs). They also serve as a crucial backstop for last-minute power procurement and help manage real-time demand-supply mismatches. With variable renewable energy now contributing over [12% of India's annual generation](#), short-term markets are also becoming vital for managing weather-driven fluctuations.

Short-term markets are essential for enabling a more flexible and responsive grid. They provide real-time price signals that reflect the system's needs, guiding optimal resource addition.

In India, the electricity market is considered *short-term* when power is traded under contracts for less than one year. Short-term transactions currently account for approximately [12.5% of the total electricity traded](#), with the remaining tied up in longer-term contracts, such as multi-year PPAs.

The short-term power market in India primarily comprises bilateral trades (often through trading licensees), [power exchange](#) transactions (multiple buyers and sellers place competitive bids) and ex-post deviation settlements under the [Deviation Settlement Mechanism \(DSM\)](#). The Central Electricity Regulatory Commission (CERC) introduced the ancillary or grid balancing services markets in 2023, but traded volumes remain limited.

The volume of electricity traded on Indian power exchanges has more than doubled between 2019 and 2024, now accounting for around [6% of total electricity transactions](#) in India. While this may seem small in percentage terms, it translates to a volume of approximately 121 TWh, equivalent to the entire annual [electricity generation of the Netherlands](#).

The [Indian Energy Exchange \(IEX\)](#) accounts for around [84% of total energy](#) traded on power exchanges and [nearly 100% share](#) in the Day Ahead Market (DAM) segment. While the DAM remains the most widely used segment, power

exchanges have introduced several new segments, such as the Real-Time Market (RTM) and the Term Ahead Market (TAM), since 2022.

Electricity volumes on Indian power exchanges has more than doubled in the last five years

Electricity transacted over Indian power exchanges, TWh

Source: Report on Short-term Power Market in India: 2023-24 · Volume includes trading across all power exchanges- Indian Energy Exchange (IEX), Power Exchange India Limited (PXIL), and Hindustan Power Exchange (HPX)

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2.1.2. Growing troughs and peaks: Understanding past trends

In 2025, there have been several [mid-day price crashes](#) across market segments. [Unexpectedly low demand](#) due to unseasonal rains, combined with surplus mid-day generation, particularly from solar, were the key drivers of the crashes. Interestingly, on many of the same days, prices surged in the evening, often touching the market price cap.

For instance, in the [IEX-DAM](#), on 25th–26th May and 1st–2nd June 2025 (coinciding with Sunday–Monday), mid-day prices hovered between INR 0 and INR 0.30 per kilowatt-hours (kWh). Several similar instances occurred throughout May and June. By comparison, INR 0.30 per kWh was the lowest price recorded in

DAM during August 2024, and that was a one-off event. Also, sustained [solar curtailment](#) in the summer of 2025, combined with full compensation to generators, would technically imply the presence of negative pricing during mid-day. The sharper and more frequent dips in 2025 have heightened concerns over growing market volatility.

Mid-day price crashes, night-time spikes: Signs of growing volatility

15-minute timeblock on Indian Energy Exchange- Day Ahead Market (May 26, 2025)

Market Clearing Price (₹/kWh)

Buy Sell

Volume bids (GW)

Source: Indian Energy Exchange (IEX) · A representative day has been shown, illustrating mid-day price crashes and late evening spikes. Market Clearing Price (MCP) refers to the price at which electricity is transacted on the exchange for a specific 15-minute time block.

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While some price events in 2025 have made headlines, the underlying trend has been building for some time. A few clear patterns have emerged in DAM prices over the years: the daily price spread is increasing, with both troughs and peaks becoming more pronounced. This trend holds true on average across most months, cutting across seasonal variations.

In a power exchange, price spread is the gap between the lowest and highest hourly clearing prices over a given day.

Deeper troughs, higher peaks: Price extremes are becoming the norm on Indian power exchanges

Monthly average MCP (INR/kWh) across time blocks on IEX- Day Ahead Market

Shaded area represents the min-max range for 2019-2021

2022 2023 2024 2025

Source: Indian Energy Exchange (IEX) · Market Clearing Price (MCP) refers to the price at which electricity is transacted on the exchange for a specific 15-minute time block. Here, MCPs are averaged for each time block across all days in a month to generate the typical hourly price profile for that month in a given year.

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In January, the gap between the average mid-day and late evening prices rose from INR 1.5/kWh in 2019 to INR 5.5/kWh in 2025, a 24% annual increase. In June, this gap jumped from INR 2.5/kWh to INR 7.5/kWh, reflecting a 17% rise.

A closer look at price extremes further highlights this trend. Since 2022, peak prices above INR 9/kWh have occurred around 6,500 times annually, nearly 18% of all time blocks. Meanwhile, ultra-low prices below INR 1/kWh are rising quickly, from 375 instances in 2024 to 514 in just the first half of 2025.

Electricity price crashes are becoming frequent in India, while price spikes persist

Cumulative number of 15-minute time blocks on the Indian Energy Exchange witnessing price crashes (MCP < INR 1/kWh) and price peaks (MCP > INR 9/kWh)

Instances of price crashes

Instances of price peaks

Source: Indian Energy Exchange (IEX) - Market Clearing Price (MCP) refers to the price at which electricity is transacted on the exchange for a specific 15-minute time block. MCP data is till June 2025. The price cap for the Day Ahead Market was revised from INR 12/kWh to INR 10/kWh in March 2023.

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One thing is clear: such market swings are no longer isolated events; they are becoming a regular feature on India's power exchanges.

2.1.3. The outlook on price volatility: Decoding the future

The outlook for price volatility is a key factor in guiding investments in merchant BESS, whose revenues rely on sustained price arbitrage. It is not just the current price arbitrage that matters, but also the underlying drivers. The future will depend on how these drivers shape up with shifts in the electricity mix, market dynamics and the regulatory environment.

1. Rising solar penetration during mid-day:

Increasing solar generation is leading to surplus, zero marginal cost generation during mid-day hours. Also, thermal generators under fixed contracts are often

forced to back down and operate near their [minimum technical load](#) (MTL). To avoid a complete shutdown, many shift to the short-term power markets, offering power at very low prices simply to stay operational. This tends to further push down mid-day prices.

As more solar capacity comes online, such price crashes are likely to become routine, mirroring trends observed in other [high-solar markets like Spain](#). Changing regulations around the MTL of thermal power plants and emerging [mandates for two-part operations](#) will also be key in shaping future mid-day price profiles.

2. High evening demand and rigidity of the thermal fleet:

Several factors drive elevated evening prices. Demand typically peaks during this period, especially in summer, pushing higher-cost generators to set the market clearing price. More importantly, as aforementioned, with rising solar penetration, many thermal generators operate at or near their MTL during the day. To avoid uneconomic operation, some may shut down entirely for the day.

As a result, two effects emerge by evening that lead to price spikes:

- **First**, generators that were offline during the day are not immediately available to supply power during the evening.
- **Second**, those that continued operating at low output may offer power at higher prices to recoup their costs.

Looking ahead, understanding how power exchange prices evolve will depend on factors such as the mix and capacity of generators operating across different times of day, the profile of buy and sell bids and seasonal demand variations. On average, price peaks and troughs are likely to grow more pronounced. However, India's price caps and floors may dampen extreme volatility compared to more liberalised markets like [Australia](#).

Mid-day prices are likely to remain suppressed on India's power exchanges over the coming years

Expected Day-Ahead Market prices (INR/kWh) for January and June 2030, with confidence intervals (CI)

-75% CI -50% CI Forecast for 2030 +50% CI +75% CI

Ember's price forecast is based on the BattMan model which considers expected changes in the generation mix, along with historical power prices and demand-supply patterns observed on the Indian Energy Exchange- Day Ahead Market (IEX-DAM). This chart illustrates a representative month—January and June—for the year 2030, chosen to demonstrate typical future trends.

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While price volatility is likely to increase due to the reasons explained, its exact trajectory remains uncertain. Though forecasting future prices with accuracy is inherently challenging, certain variables like demand patterns, the evolving generation mix and system flexibility will shape overall trends. Therefore, considering a range of price scenarios is necessary when building a robust outlook for battery revenues.

2.1.4. Why taming price volatility will be important for renewable growth

Large fluctuations or volatility in prices can disrupt any market. Buyers and sellers depend on a certain level of price predictability to plan their procurement and operations.

The following are some of the challenges linked to high market volatility that could hold back India's power sector transition:

1. Uncertainty for sellers: Growing disconnect between the cost of generation and the revenue realised

Frequent price crashes can severely impact the cash flows of existing merchant generators and discourage new capacity from entering the power markets. This affects all types of merchant generators – solar, hydro and thermal. The impact is often more pronounced for solar. This is because price crashes typically occur during mid-day hours, when solar output is at its peak. To understand this phenomenon more clearly, the capture rate metric is often used in electricity markets.

Capture rate is the average price an electricity generator actually earns compared to the average market price during the same period. In other words, it shows how well a generator is capturing the value of electricity in the market. A low capture rate means the generator is producing most of its power when prices are low. This isn't a good thing for its financial viability.

In India, solar's share in total generation rose from 3.3% in 2019 to 7.4% in 2024, while the estimated average annual capture rate on the IEX Day Ahead Market dropped from 93% to 70% in the same interval. This reflects reduced price value

during peak solar hours. This trend will likely exacerbate as mid-day surplus generation increases.

Solar capture rate declines have been a common phenomenon across high solar geographies. For example, [in Spain, the capture rate fell](#) from nearly 100% in 2021 to 40% in April 2024, marked by a threefold rise in installed solar capacity.

Surplus solar generation shrinks revenue for standalone solar participating in Indian power exchanges

Capture rate (%)

Share generation from solar (%)

Source: Ember- India Electricity Data Explorer · The capture rate is the ratio of the average market price actually earned by a solar generator to the overall average market price. Here, the monthly capture rate is modelled using Ember's BattMan model using hourly solar share in the generation mix and Day-Ahead Market (DAM) prices from the Indian Energy Exchange (IEX) for each month.

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Clearly, falling capture rates affect the profitability of merchant solar, which is primarily designed to operate in power exchanges. However, a more pressing concern is the impact on the tariffs and financial viability of India's emerging firm and [dispatchable renewable energy \(FDRE\) capacity](#), a class of projects aiming to deliver round-the-clock clean power.

FDRE projects are typically oversized in renewable capacity to meet firm supply obligations under long-term PPAs. As a design principle, surplus generation (~ [25 to 45% of total generation](#)) is intended to be sold on short-term power markets.

Falling capture rates and declining revenue realisation from these markets may force developers to raise PPA tariffs to ensure project viability. This could meet regulatory pushback and raise broader concerns about the cost-competitiveness of India's FDRE experiment.

2. Uncertainty for buyers: Dealing with the unpredictability of power markets

In the IEX DAM, the major buyers of electricity are state-owned distribution companies (74%), private distribution licensees (13.4%) and the remaining from commercial and industrial (C&I) open access consumers.

There are broadly two key concerns arising from sharper price volatility in the power exchanges:

- **Hesitation in long-term renewable contracts:**

Distribution utilities may hesitate to sign long-term PPAs for solar power (or projects with a significant solar component) if they expect to consistently procure the same power from exchanges at lower prices. This could undermine the traditional PPA-based renewable model.

- **Stress buying during peak demand:**

Electricity distribution companies (DISCOMs) often turn to power exchanges to manage peak demand or cover inadvertent shortfalls. When this becomes reactive stress buying rather than part of a planned procurement, it pushes up the average cost of power for DISCOMs.

Given the ability of batteries to perform price arbitrage, batteries can not only generate revenue from the market inefficiency, but also help reduce price volatility over time. This is not just a commercial advantage anymore; it's a system-level solution they offer.

But that's only part of their value stack. Their ability to store energy and ramp quickly can fundamentally reshape how grid balancing reserves have worked in India. The next section provides a closer look.

2.2. The challenge of grid frequency fluctuations

Grid frequency is a critical indicator of the health of the power system. Frequency reflects the balance between supply and demand. Deviations beyond acceptable limits can compromise reliability.

As per the [Indian Electricity Grid Code](#), the acceptable frequency range is 49.90 Hz to 50.05 Hz, with 50 Hz as the national reference frequency. A sustained mismatch between electricity demand and supply can lead to prolonged frequency excursions beyond the permissible range. Such imbalances typically stem from unplanned outages or errors in load (or generation) forecasting.

There have been growing concerns around [frequency excursions in India](#) for some of these reasons. Ideally, grid frequency should stay within the permissible range even when supply-demand mismatches occur. When it does not, the root cause is often a lack of adequate grid balancing resources, also known as ancillary services.

Long periods outside the acceptable frequency range signal the need for more grid balancing reserves in India

Frequency profile (in Hz) of the Indian grid on selected days in May 2025 that witnessed significant deviations

Source: Grid-India · The Indian Electricity Grid Code (IEGC) sets the national reference frequency at 50 Hz and defines the acceptable operating range as 49.90 to 50.05 Hz.

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[Ancillary services](#) include primary response (typically built into generators as per the grid code and serve as the first line of defence), secondary reserve (responds within 30 seconds using standby generators, BESS or demand response to restore frequency) and tertiary reserve (engaged within 15 minutes for sustained support, generally coal or hydro generators).

These ancillary services can be UP (to increase supply during shortfalls) or DOWN (to reduce supply during surpluses), helping maintain balance between demand and supply in real time. This ensures the stability and reliability of the grid.

Rising variable renewable energy is also reshaping grid dynamics. During summer mid-days, solar peaks often force coal plants to ramp down power generation to or below their technical minimum. During these periods, the grid lacks sufficient downward ancillary reserves, since most thermal units are [already operating near their minimum](#) or are shut down.

Conversely, in the evening and night hours, when demand surges, these same coal plants are pushed to full output, while the plants that were down cannot start in time to generate. This leaves little headroom to provide upward reserves to meet any additional demand or unexpected events.

India's grid faces reliability concerns due to insufficient ancillary reserves – BESS offers a strategic solution

Available versus required reserves for UP and DOWN regulation (in MW)

Source: Grid-India · UP regulation refers to an increase in power output when demand rises or supply drops, while DOWN regulation refers to a decrease in power output during low demand or excess supply. BESS refers to Battery Energy Storage Systems.

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This limited ability to ramp down at noon and ramp up at night highlights a key structural gap in India's ancillary services mechanism, which remains dominated by conventional generators, primarily coal-based.

For instance, on 26 May 2025, both upward and downward spinning reserves were inadequate. Downward reserves were near zero for five mid-day hours, while upward reserves were zero for three hours late at night. Such conditions expose the grid to unexpected outages, with limited capacity to restore balance quickly. Such instances have become more frequent and now represent [systemic issues](#).

2.2.1. Concerns over reserve adequacy and response speed point towards a greater role for batteries

Coal and hydro generators [primarily serve India's ancillary reserves](#), with some contribution from gas. This pattern has persisted due to the regulatory framework that historically allowed only certain types of generators to participate.

India has managed the provision of ancillary services through an administrative mechanism known as [RRAS \(Reserves Regulation Ancillary Services\)](#). The system operator primarily relied on conventional generators, typically those whose tariffs were regulated by the government, to provide for slow tertiary reserves.

While RRAS improved India's frequency profile to some extent, [it faced key limitations](#):

- Limited availability during peak demand, as it relied on surplus generator capacity, which was often unavailable when most needed.
- Used for routine balancing rather than true contingencies, diluting its intended role.
- Lack of fast response, since conventional generators were often too slow to address real-time frequency deviations effectively.

The limitations of RRAS highlighted the need for faster, more flexible reserves and stronger incentives for participation. A shift towards more [market-based ancillary services](#) was needed to allow resources to compete based on cost and performance.

Grid Controller of India (GRID India) introduced two key mechanisms in 2023 to change under India's ancillary services framework:

- [SRAS \(Secondary Reserve Ancillary Services\)](#): Designed for fast response to contingencies, with dispatch based on ramping speed and cost. This prioritised the fastest and most cost-effective resource. SRAS allows

participation from batteries, pumped hydro and demand response.

- [TRAS \(Tertiary Reserve Ancillary Services\)](#): Envisioned as a day-ahead market where grid operators procure reserves for shortfall through competitive bidding.

These early discussions have opened the door for fast-acting reserves like BESS to help fill the growing gap in grid stability. It is now up to the market to determine whether existing mechanisms, such as those under SRAS, are sufficient to support full participation in the ancillary services market.

Current incentive structures without any [capacity payment](#) for BESS may not yet be well-aligned for it to participate exclusively in ancillary services. However, solutions exist, and this is where effective marketcraft becomes essential.

As discussed earlier, mid-day oversupply on the grid is a condition that will likely intensify in the future. In such scenarios, a BESS can absorb excess electricity at little to no cost, essentially charging for free. It can then sell the stored energy into other market segments, such as the DAM. This ability to buy and sell across different market segments forms the foundation of value stacking of BESS, which is key to managing its economics.

Merchant batteries poised for attractive returns in India

With the regulatory groundwork in place and the economics now compelling, merchant BESS is poised to balance a renewables-heavy grid while delivering an IRR of up to 24%.

Battery storage in India has moved from a promising technology to a fully bankable grid asset. A significant drop in battery costs and widening wholesale-price spreads mean a well-operated system can cover its expenses and still deliver attractive profits. DAM volatility offers reliable arbitrage income, while ancillary markets also create opportunities to earn additional revenue. Even under conservative assumptions, batteries show attractive returns across varying cost and efficiency levels, with shorter-duration BESS showing better revenue prospects.

3.1. Battery storage economics in power markets

Merchant BESS earns through two market streams: DAM and Ancillary Services Market. In the DAM, they act as price-responsive traders, charging when prices are low and discharging when prices are high. Arbitrage is profitable when revenues exceed charging costs and the battery's levelised cost of storage (LCOS). Participation in the ancillary services market can also provide additional revenue opportunities.

[Levelised Cost of Storage \(LCOS\)](#) refers to the average cost of storing and delivering one unit of electricity over the battery's lifetime. It includes capital and financing costs, operating and maintenance costs and degradation effects, but does not include the cost of charging the battery.

3.1.1. How the arbitrage play works in the wholesale electricity market

BESS can buy power while charging and sell while discharging, enabling revenue through price arbitrage. However, for this to be economically viable, revenue from selling has to be greater than the costs (cost of buying electricity + cost of losses + LCOS).

The chart below illustrates how a 2-hour battery can capture DAM price spreads over three days in June, using [2024 IEX-DAM prices](#). For example, during solar hours, the market clears at roughly INR 2.6/kWh, where the battery charges (blue bar).

Since a battery typically has a round-trip efficiency of 85%, it loses some energy during the charge-discharge cycle. Therefore, if it buys electricity at INR 2.6/kWh, the actual cost per kWh of electricity stored is INR 3.06/kWh (INR 2.6 per kWh/85%). But the effective cost of the electricity delivered should also include the BESS LCOS, which we estimate to be around INR 4.5/kWh. Therefore, the effective cost of delivered electricity for this instance is INR 3.06/kWh + INR 4.5/kWh = INR 7.56/kWh. Therefore, the battery makes a profit when it can sell above this price, i.e., INR 7.56/kWh.

An opportunity for batteries: Revenue from discharging can outweigh the costs of charging

Simulation of Battery Energy Storage system (BESS) operating in India's day ahead market

IEX DAM Price for 3 days in June 2025 (INR/kWh)

Charge and Discharge schedule of a BESS participating in the IEX DAM

Charging cost and discharging revenue of a BESS participating in the IEX DAM

Source: Dispatch and revenue estimation based on hourly simulations of a 2-hour BESS using Ember's BattMan model for three days in June 2025. IEX-DAM represents the Day-Ahead Market prices on the Indian Energy Exchange

For example, on selling at INR 10/kWh, the selling price of electricity (INR/kWh) would provide a net profit of nearly INR 2.5/kWh for the battery asset for this particular cycle.

3.1.2. The potential revenue from ancillary market participation

Batteries in ancillary service markets can end up getting paid to charge, converting charging from an expense into a source of income.

BESS can potentially get paid to charge in the SRAS-Down market

In the [SRAS-Down](#) (where an online reserve is instructed to back down or absorb excess power present in the system) market, a merchant BESS can charge without paying for the electricity and can even earn a bonus of up to INR 0.50/kWh if it closely follows the dispatch instructions issued. Specifically, if it maintains [an accuracy of over 95%](#) in tracking the instructed charge profile throughout the day, it qualifies for the full bonus.

BESS can get paid to charge in the emergency TRAS-Down market in future

In the emergency TRAS-Down market, BESS can become a cost-saving substitute to curtailing variable renewable generation. When there is not enough tertiary reserve available through the TRAS-down market, the grid operator can force generators (mostly renewable energy generators) to curtail their generation during oversupply conditions. This curtailment is settled at the declared cost of generation. These generators are therefore paid their full energy charge (often INR 2–3 /kWh) for every unit they are forced to back down from.

If, instead, the grid operator directs BESS to absorb that surplus, the same unit of electricity can potentially be settled at rates far lower than what the operator may pay the renewable generator to compensate for curtailment.

3.2. Merchant BESS is financially viable 2024 onwards

3.2.1. Higher potential revenues and falling battery costs have made merchant BESS commercially viable

Merchant battery storage in India has reached a critical juncture. Starting in 2024, expected annual revenues exceeded annualised costs for the first time. In the graph below, the cost reflects the yearly expense of installing and operating a battery in a particular year, while the revenue represents what a merchant battery could have earned from energy market participation.

Batteries installed in India post-2024 are projected to be profitable

For merchant batteries operating in the day-ahead market

Source: Revenue estimated for best-in-class BESS performance using Ember's BattMan model and IEX market data. Annualised cost represents the yearly capital and operating cost of a BESS commissioned in the respective year. Cost estimates are based on tender data when available; otherwise, global benchmarks are used. Revenue reflects earnings from BESS operation in that year from participating in the IEX DAM

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80% reduction in BESS costs and a fivefold increase in merchant BESS revenue in the last decade

Over the past decade, battery costs have declined [significantly](#) from around INR 7.9 million/megawatt-hour (MWh) in 2015 to INR 1.7 million/MWh in 2025 (an average year-on-year decline of 14%). In parallel, revenues from market participation have increased fivefold, from INR 0.5 million/MWh in 2015 to INR 2.4 million/MWh in 2025. In 2024, estimated revenues surpassed costs for the first time, marking a fundamental shift in the business case for Merchant BESS.

Merchant BESS is no longer just a technical asset; it has become a commercially viable investment opportunity.

A sharp rise in revenue opportunities in the DAM has largely enabled the shift to profitability. Growing price spreads now allow storage assets to consistently buy low and sell high.

Since early 2024, the average daily price spread in the IEX-DAM has exceeded the LCOS, driving the commercial viability of new merchant BESS projects towards the cusp of transformation.

In India, the electricity price spread exceeds the levelised cost of storage after 2024, making the arbitrage attractive

■ Levelised cost of storage (INR/kWh)
 ■ Monthly average price spread (INR/kWh)
 ■ Daily price spread (INR/kWh)

Source: IEX Day-Ahead Market prices. · Price spread refers to the difference between the highest and lowest electricity prices within a day—representing the potential margin a battery can capture by charging low and discharging high. Cost estimates are based on actual tender data for standalone BESS. The observed spread in 2022 may appear unusually high due to post-COVID recovery dynamics and the absence of a price cap during that period. A INR 12/kWh cap was introduced in April 2022 and later reduced to INR 10/kWh in March 2023, contributing to the visible decline in spreads over time.

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The figure shows the daily hourly gap between the highest and lowest DAM prices across each 24-hour cycle, the average spread across each month and the LCOS. When price spreads in the DAM consistently surpass LCOS, it signals that batteries can earn enough from pure arbitrage to recover their full lifecycle costs.

From 2022 through much of 2023, the average price spread remained below LCOS, meaning batteries deployed without other revenue stacking were unlikely

to be financially viable. Since early 2024, however, the widening price spreads driven by increased renewable penetration have flipped that equation, making merchant battery storage a viable standalone business model, even without ancillary service revenues or contracted offtake.

3.3. BESS investments are an attractive asset class today

Returns of up to 24% are achievable from an investment made in merchant BESS in 2025

Merchant BESS commissioned at 2024 costs will be profitable assets and can deliver strong returns through a combination of DAM arbitrage and ancillary market revenues, according to our projections. Since the majority of BESS revenues come from price spreads in the IEX DAM, understanding how these price profiles may evolve is critical. Key factors such as seasonal demand patterns, the changing generation mix and regulatory shifts will influence future price formation. Any outlook must therefore be grounded in price forecasts with associated confidence intervals. Optimistic and conservative arbitrage estimates depend on the ability to assess both upside and downside scenarios within this price range.

The ability to participate in both the day-ahead and ancillary services market can improve returns for battery projects

Financial assessment of a BESS project commissioned in 2025 in India

Source: Results from Ember's BattMan model. Based on a Battery Energy Storage System (BESS) project commissioned in 2025 with a 2-hour storage duration. This analysis assumes BESS participation in the Day-Ahead Market (DAM) and SRAS-Down, with 2024 cost benchmarks and projected revenues over 10 years. Price forecasts are based on two scenarios: a conservative case with moderate spreads reflecting 2023–24 market stability, and an optimistic case with higher volatility driven by renewable oversupply and peak demand spikes, leading to wider intraday spreads.

Arbitrage in the Day Ahead Market contributes nearly 80–85% of total earnings, while ancillary services account for the remaining 15–20%. Under optimistic assumptions, annual revenues reach INR 3.3 million/MWh, pushing project internal rates of returns (IRRs) to ~24%.

Even under conservative price spreads, returns remain strong at 21%, but with a larger share of earnings coming from incentives linked to ancillary market participation.

Even under the more conservative price-spread assumptions, the battery generates INR 3.2 million/MWh per year, nearly double the annualised cost of owning and operating a 2024-vintage system (~INR 1.7 million/MWh). That

differential pushes the IRR well above typical debt costs, yielding a decent equity-level return.

3.4. The parameters that affect returns

The next question is what determines how much a merchant BESS can actually earn under uncertainty? Two key sets of factors shape this outcome. The first relates to cost and technical performance, like [round-trip efficiency](#) and [depth of discharge](#), which may vary during real-world operation. The second is design choices, particularly storage duration, which impacts how much of the daily price spread a battery can capture. The following analysis explores these critical levers through a series of sensitivity tests on IRR for a merchant BESS project.

Round-trip efficiency (RTE), measured as a percentage, is a ratio of the energy charged to the battery to the energy discharged from the battery.

Depth of Discharge (DoD) refers to the percentage of a battery's total capacity that has been used or discharged relative to its full capacity.

A detailed explanation of variations in capital costs and technical parameters such as depth of discharge (DoD) and round-trip efficiency (RTE), as well as the relationship between storage duration, associated costs and operational capabilities, are available [here](#).

3.4.1. BESS delivers attractive returns even under conditions of cost uncertainty and technical variability

Different variables, both financial and technical, can significantly affect the returns of a BESS project. These include upfront capital costs, system efficiency (RTE) and operational parameters, such as DoD. While these factors are typically

estimated during the design stage, real-world performance often diverges once the project is implemented.

The following analysis explores the impact of variation in system cost, DoD and RTE on the IRR of a merchant BESS (2-hour) project that earns revenue solely from price arbitrage in the DAM, without stacking additional income streams from ancillary markets. We focus only on DAM revenues, excluding ancillary services or other income streams, to isolate the impact of these technical and cost parameters on project returns.

Return on merchant BESS in India is resilient across key technical and cost sensitivities

Internal rate of return (%) from day-ahead market (DAM) participation under sensitivity analysis for depth of discharge (DoD), cost, round-trip efficiency (RTE)

Source: Results from Ember's BattMan model · The dotted line represents the base case IRR of ~17%

The analysis is based on a 2-hour Battery Energy Storage System (BESS), with IRR sensitivity evaluated across variations in depth of discharge (85–95%, base 90%), round-trip efficiency (80–90%, base 85%), and capital cost ($\pm 5\%$ from base)

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The analysis tests the following variations:

- Capital cost: INR 10 million/MWh (2 hours) $\pm 5\%$
- DoD: Base value (90%) $\pm 5\%$

- RTE: Base value (85%) $\pm 5\%$

A $\pm 5\%$ shift in any of the tested parameters moves the IRR by only about ± 1 percentage point from the base case IRR of 17% (i.e., only considering DAM participation).

While not a strictly equivalent comparison, applying a 5% variation to each parameter (system cost, DoD and RTE) results in a similar impact on IRR. Yet, the overall uncertainty introduced remains limited, with IRR fluctuating by only $\pm 2\%$. This indicates that BESS projects can maintain attractive returns despite variability across cost and technical parameters.

3.4.2. Shorter-duration merchant BESS shows slightly higher returns

Merchant battery returns vary by duration, but shorter-duration merchant BESS will likely deliver a higher upside by combining the DAM and ancillary market revenue. This is largely due to their ability to precisely target the most extreme price differentials within a given day. Shorter-duration BESS can deliver higher returns in markets with sharp, short-lived price peaks and troughs, as they use the same power capacity over less energy to target the steepest price spreads—without needing to operate during flatter periods.

While the difference in IRR between 1-hour and 2-hour systems is not substantial, the IRR for 4-hour systems can be notably lower.

Short-duration merchant BESS shows higher upside potential for Indian power markets

Range of internal rate of return (in %), by BESS duration

Source: Results from Ember's BattMan model · The IRR range is for price scenarios across market segments (Day Ahead and Ancillary markets). Duration of a Battery Energy Storage System (BESS) refers to how long the battery can discharge at its rated power before being fully depleted.

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Whether shorter or longer-duration BESS is better depends on the shape of the price curve, specifically, the difference between the set of highest and lowest price hours, the duration of those price signals and capital cost per MWh of storage.

Several markets, including Germany, the UK, Spain, and California, are seeing a [shift toward longer-duration battery storage](#) as sustained periods of high and low prices enhance the value of systems capable of operating across extended intervals.

Merchant batteries deliver critical system-level value

The strong business case for merchant BESS offers the chance for batteries to fulfil their long-held promise of being critical to support a high-renewables grid.

The multi-faceted benefits of battery storage to support a high-renewables grid have never been in doubt. Yet, despite its benefits to the grid, prohibitively high upfront costs and the lack of a business case to invest in the deployment of battery storage have prevented its penetration in the Indian electricity system till now.

The strengthening business for battery storage comes at an apt time. With rising price volatility and the growing need for fast-acting reserves, the case for battery storage is clear. They deliver critical system-level value in two key areas:

- **Reducing price volatility and improving liquidity in short-term markets:**
A liquid short-term market with stable prices is vital for renewable energy growth. It serves as a backstop for power purchase in case of demand-supply mismatch, thereby building greater confidence to integrate higher shares of renewables.

Also, power market sales form a key revenue stream for FDRE projects, so avoiding consistently low prices during solar hours is essential to keep these projects viable and tariffs affordable.

- **Enabling fast response for real-time grid balancing**

Systemic grid fluctuations are expected to intensify due to the inflexibility of coal and the growing share of renewables in the energy mix. Sufficient fast-acting reserves will be essential to maintain grid stability. While batteries are eligible to participate in India's Secondary Reserve Ancillary Services (SRAS) market, incentive mechanisms need to be improved further to encourage batteries to play a greater role in grid balancing services.

Recently, India hit a milestone of 50% non-fossil fuel power generation capacity. The ability of its electricity grid to keep accommodating more variable renewable energy will depend on whether developers, investors and stakeholders are able to accelerate the dawn of the age of battery storage.

Methodology

The analysis was carried out using Ember's Battery Modelling Suite (BattMan), a comprehensive tool designed to optimise the operation and sizing of Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS) across multiple revenue streams. At its core is the Battery Modelling Module, which performs detailed dispatch and sizing optimisation. It comprises the following key modules:

- **Battery optimisation:**
For this report, we optimise BESS operation to maximise revenue through participation in the Day-Ahead Market (DAM) and SRAS-Down ancillary service. Technically, the concept can be extended across multiple market segments based on the availability of data.
- **Price forecasting:**
Generates forward-looking electricity price projections using historical trends, seasonal demand-supply variations, and changes in the generation mix. These forecasts serve as essential inputs to the DAM and ancillary service market optimisation.
- **Financial analysis of battery projects:**
Converts technical outputs into detailed project-level financial metrics such as IRR, payback period and discounted cash flow. This provides a comprehensive techno-economic assessment of a BESS project.
- **Sensitivity analysis:**
Tests the robustness of project outcomes by analysing how ~10+ key

technical, market, and financial variables affect returns—highlighting risks and resilience in different scenarios.

A detailed description of the data, methods and inputs used can be found [here](#).

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Photo

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